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Stimulating economic growth in the least developed countries: Direct cash transfers for the retired via mobile phones

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Abstract

The result of current aid policies is that only a small percentage of foreign aid reaches the poorest of the poor in the least developed countries. Current trends of urbanisation and self-reliance place elderly people in an increasingly difficult situation. This paper aims to stimulate debate by introducing an alternative mechanism for foreign aid. With the help of an economic model, we demonstrate how direct cash transfers to elderly people can spur economic growth. Targeting all elderly people above a certain age minimises selection costs and removes perverse incentives. The use of new mobile phone technologies reduces transaction costs and makes our proposed modality feasible including in the least developed countries with low functioning governments.

Key words

Direct cash transfers, foreign aid, least developed countries, economic growth, elderly people, mobile phone

1. Introduction

The effectiveness of foreign aid in achieving the objective of economic growth in the least developed countries is questionable (Halder 2003, Maes and Foose 2006). At the same time, a large percentage of aid budgets are being consumed by the development industry, whereas only a small percentage actually reaches the target beneficiaries. Consequently, a situation of aid fatigue in donor countries is evolving, resulting in decreasing aid transfers from OECD countries (OECD 2008). It is time to rethink current foreign-aid modalities and search for alternatives. This paper addresses the most obvious and simple questions: “Can we give the money directly to the poor?” and “Could that action foment economic growth?”

An affirmative answer to these questions has been obstructed by arguments regarding moral hazard, work disincentives, and high transaction costs (Grosch 1994, Caldes and Maluccio 2004, Schubert and Slater 2006). Moreover, it would be a political and developmental advantage if the recipients of the money were, at least on average, among the poorest.

This paper develops a theoretical model that illustrates the ways in which economic growth can be stimulated by a new aid modality consisting of direct cash transfers to elderly people. The current trends of urbanisation and self-reliance place elderly people in an increasingly difficult situation (Aborderin 2004); the elderly, on average, are among the poorest of the poor (Barrientos, Gorman et al. 2003). Thus, to keep selection costs low, we suggest targeting all elderly people above a certain age that should be defined locally. Moreover, applying new mobile-phone technology to transfer the funds minimises any transaction costs. Additionally, because the majority of elderly people are retired, we overcome work-disincentive problems. Our aim is to stimulate debate by questioning the established aid paradigms and demonstrating that more growth-effective and cost-efficient alternatives may be available.

Section 2 of this paper identifies the need for a new aid modality and describes the ways in which cash transfers to the elderly could be a new aid alternative. Section 3 explains the new mobile phone technology and the feasibility of using this technology to wire money directly to elderly people. Section 4 provides related evidence from cash-transfer schemes and international remittances. Section 5 sets up our model, and Section 6 presents our conclusions.

2. Need for a new aid modality

Whereas some developing countries, most notably China and India, have experienced strong economic growth in the past several years, the majority of low-income countries have been unable to sustain strong economic growth and reduce internal poverty (Lin and Rosenblatt 2012). There is a need for economic policies that can foster growth and development (Clifton 2012), and these policies should include new foreign aid policies. Nevertheless, horror stories of corruption, high overhead costs, swollen donor and multilateral organisations, and minimal aid reaching the very poorest people are increasingly leading to a feeling of aid fatigue in donor countries. Only one-fourth of OECD aid is reaching the least developed countries (OECD 2008). In 2007, OECD countries provided US\$103.7 billion in aid. In real terms, foreign aid decreased 5.1% from 2005 to 2006 and an additional 8.4% from 2006 to 2007 (OECD, 2008). After the financial crisis, additional declines in aid were observed; OECD reports that foreign aid fell 3% in 2011.¹ Because of a considerable increase in debt forgiveness and support to countries such as Iraq and Afghanistan, the ratio of aid to gross national income (GNI) fluctuates near 0.3%, which is an improvement from the all-time low ratio of 0.22% in 1999-2001. However, this aid ratio is well below the UN target of 0.7% and considerably lower than the ratio in the 1970s, 1980s, and early 1990s, when the ratio fluctuated near 0.35% (OECD 2008).

¹ OECD newsroom: "Development: Aid to developing countries falls because of global recession." (www.oecd.org/newsroom).

Faced with aid fatigue, donor countries continue with business as usual, which means the inclusion of several stakeholders, the unclear distribution of responsibilities between donors and recipient countries/organisations, and bureaucratic procedures and organisation. As a result, only a minor percentage of aid budgets is actually transposed into direct benefits for the target group, i.e., the poorest people in the least developed countries. The question remains as to how long the necessary public support in donor countries will uphold this aid regime.

Many scholars have examined the issue of whether foreign aid has a positive effect on economic growth (for an excellent overview see McGillivray, Feeny et al. 2006). One stream of literature claims that aid enhances economic growth by complementing domestic resources and supplementing domestic savings, whereas another stream argues that aid has a significant negative effect because it is consumed and substitutes for domestic resources.

The most disputed argument is whether supportive local macroeconomic conditions are necessary for aid to have an effect (Halder 2003, Maes and Foose 2006). According to one claim, aid can be beneficial in supportive environments, whereas aid is often ineffective and has a negative effect on economic growth in poor environments. Based on this outlook, aid therefore spurs growth only when sound economic policies are in place before its provision.

Several researchers note that aid can be an effective instrument for triggering economic growth (World-Bank 1997, Dunford 2002). However, no consensus has been reached, and those scholars who assert that aid has no effect continue to hold considerable ground (McGillivray, Feeny et al. 2006). One policy implication is that only approximately one-fourth of OECD aid reaches the least developed countries in which poor environments are most notable (OECD 2008).

The aim of this paper is not to take a stand in the debate regarding whether aid enhances growth. We simply argue that it is time to present alternatives to the present aid regimes. To accomplish this goal, we develop a model to illustrate that direct cash transfers to elderly people can promote economic growth in countries with weak policy regimes. We believe that such alternatives are needed to uphold the general public support for foreign aid in donor countries. Taxpayers, who are also voters, may not continue to allow three-fourths of foreign aid to be consumed by bureaucrats and recipients in better-off countries, rather than to benefit the poorest people in the least developed countries.

With the exception of emergency aid, the aim of the majority of foreign development aid is to stimulate economic growth by strengthening the supply side of national economies. Aid enables countries to improve educational systems, build roads, adopt legal frameworks, make financial services available, and install production facilities, hypothetically driving economic growth by increasing and improving supply. However, many researchers have begun to question this conventional view and have advocated demand-led growth as a development strategy (Setterfield 2002).

The recent emergence of direct cash-transfer programmes can be considered a practical response to the need for demand-led growth strategies. Supporters argue that direct cash transfers to poor people do not have to be counterproductive and do not necessarily carry an inflationary risk (Farrington and Slater 2006, Hanlon, Barrientos et al. 2010). However, the primary argument in support of cash transfer programmes is that the programmes provide social protection for such extremely poor groups as children, in the form of schooling, and former soldiers, through cash for work. Another important group of cash transfer programmes includes those that condition the uptake of health interventions such as vaccines or pregnancy care (Lagarde, Haines et al. 2007). Few internationally funded cash transfer programmes have been designed with the simple objective of spurring an economy's

overall economic growth (Hanlon, Barrientos et al. 2010). The conditionality that is present in most cash transfer programmes makes them bureaucratic, ineffective, and inefficient. Their main concerns are to install selection mechanisms to reach only specific target groups, to justify their expenditures for public budgets, and to avoid moral hazard (Farrington and Slater 2006, Schubert and Slater 2006). Moral hazard refers to situations in which beneficiaries decrease their personal efforts to improve their economic situations as a result of outside support. Moreover, existent cash transfer programmes, with their various conditions, are unlikely to be successful in countries with low-functioning governments because the programmes require political support (Hanlon, Barrientos et al. 2010).

This paper's main concern is not social protection. Rather, our main reason for suggesting cash transfers to elderly people is the fact that their working capacity is limited. This factor reduces disincentives to work and thus the risk of moral hazard. Moreover, we advocate providing the transfer to all elderly people, including those who are not among the poorest, because this objective criterion ensures cost-efficient operations. A major problem in many cash transfer programmes is that they provide people with incentives to remain poor to continue receiving the cash benefit. Because the proposed new aid modality targets all elderly people above a certain age, donors will know that the majority of the recipients indeed need the cash. The program would thus give the beneficiaries no perverse incentive to remain poor, and the selection and screening costs would be close to zero. Additionally, we note that another of our selection criteria for aid would be poor countries with a need for economic growth but without an enabling environment to spur growth. If needed, our proposed modality could in principle function without any government involvement. Our concern is therefore to outline a new, cost-efficient alternative for foreign aid to enhance economic growth in the least developed countries.

However, having outlined our main motivation, we wish to acknowledge that elderly people comprise a target group that should attract more attention from policy makers and researchers. The world is experiencing a dramatic transition in demographics. By 2050, it is estimated that 80% of the 2 billion elderly people in the world will be living in developing countries in which one in five people will be more than 60 years old (Shetty 2012). Even in Africa, where fertility rates are still high, it is expected that the number of people over 60 years old will triple to 150 million by 2050 (Shetty 2012). However, in the United Nations' Millennium Development Goals, the challenge related to elderly people is not mentioned (www.un.org/millenniumgoals).

In developing countries, elderly people are generally among the poorest of the poor, and fewer than 20% receive pensions (UNFPA 2012). At the same time, elderly people can no longer take for granted a scenario in which younger generations will care for them after retirement. For example, a study from Ghana showed that resource constraints and expectations of elderly self-reliance result in less support across generations (Aborderin 2004). Thus, although the majority of elderly people in developing countries still live with younger family members, increased urbanisation and cultural changes require more attention regarding the need for elderly people to care more for themselves in the future. Therefore, the alternative aid mechanism that we present in this paper also contributes to the current debate on demographic change policy (Shetty 2012, UNFPA 2012).

3. A new, emerging technology

The original motivation for this paper was actually not the growth-aid debate, but rather the observation of the explosive development and outreach of mobile phone technologies and coverage (Khandker 2005). This phenomenon prompted us to ask whether this technology could be used to channel foreign aid directly to those whom OECD taxpayers seek to support. Achieving this objective has previously been thwarted not only by arguments

of moral hazard but also by the observation that the transfer of money directly to poor people has to date been difficult and costly. In many developing countries, nine out of 10 people do not have a bank account or access to basic financial services (UN 2006), and the cost of conventional banking is high (Khandker 2005). Large-scale cash transfers to individuals have therefore been both difficult and costly.

This situation is now changing because of the convergence of telecommunication and financial services. Money transfers through mobile phones directly to individuals, whether they live in rural or urban areas, are becoming logistically feasible at very low costs even in the poorest countries. According to the International Telecommunication Union (ITU), there are more than 6 billion mobile phone subscriptions in the world and 79% of the population in developing countries have access to a mobile phone (ITU 2011). Africa has more than 500 million mobile phone users (Rao 2011), and elderly people are gradually obtaining access to mobile phones either individually or through neighbours and family members.

This rapid technological development, together with the steep increase in mobile-phone coverage, opens up an enormous set of new opportunities. Banks have already begun to use the mobile phone infrastructure and have developed systems to wire monies to SIM cards. The uptake of the new technology is rapid. For example, in Kenya, Vodaphone reached 1 million users in only nine months with a product called M-Pesa (Khandker 2005); after a few years in partnership with Equity Bank, the company has now 14 million M-Pesa users (www.equitybank.co.ke). Vodaphone and other mobile phone companies are partnering with international commercial banks to enable international cash transfers using mobile phones as a platform.

The new technology challenges the traditional boundaries between the banking and telecom industries. For example, in 2008, the international telecom company Telenor took

over Tameer Microfinance Bank, the largest microfinance bank in Pakistan. The future of banking lies in telecom, and much future telecom business will be related to banking.

These examples illustrate a new technological reality. The technology that enables the use of mobile phones to allow cost-efficient money transfer to individuals in developing countries is already present. For the first time in history, it is now feasible to give money to poor people without encountering high transaction costs. No banks or middlemen are needed. One can now sit in London and transfer money to a person in the village of Katorongot in Kenya. The technology already exists and is increasingly being rolled out. The idea of transferring foreign aid as cash directly to individuals is therefore now feasible.

4. Related Evidence

As previously mentioned, the majority of cash transfer programmes are conditioned and aimed at poverty alleviation rather than economic growth (Hanlon, Barrientos et al. 2010). However, exceptions exist. In a pilot project in Zambia, a cash transfer programme covering the poorest 10% of the households in 143 villages and five townships was established on the premise that additional purchasing power would create multiplier effects for the local economy (Schubert and Goldberg 2004, Schubert and Slater 2006). As a December 2004 evaluation confirmed, the purchase of food, soap, blankets, and agricultural inputs stimulated the local economy. New forms of labour exchanges emerged as destitute, labour-constrained households used their cash to pay for labour to plough and weed fields. The evaluation also concluded that the transfer of cash had neither had an inflationary effect on input prices nor distorted the local labour markets (Schubert and Goldberg 2004).

The Zambian example is one among several in which cash distribution has recently been used as an alternative to other, often more problematic, aid techniques (Hanlon, Barrientos et al. 2010). However, the Zambian case is also interesting from the perspective of mobile-phone technology. According to the evaluation, a major problem for the project was

how to reach out to remote rural areas in a cost-efficient manner (Schubert and Goldberg 2004). This dilemma is in line with a common criticism of cash-transfer programmes; that is, administration costs absorb much of their budgets, which never reach the intended beneficiaries (Grosh 1994, Caldes and Maluccio 2004). Thus, recently, in better functioning developing countries like Brazil and Mexico, governments have started to transfer pensions and social benefit electronically directly to the beneficiaries (Pickens 2009). We suggest that this can be done also in the least developed countries.

Capital inflow from remittances is a parallel to foreign aid. A major difference is that remittances go directly to the end-beneficiaries, similar to what we propose to do with foreign aid. If transfers of foreign aid directly to poor people have a positive impact on economic growth, therefore so should the inflow of remittances. However, empirical studies of this approach show mixed results. In a 2005 study, Giuliano and Ruiz-Arranz found that remittances do enhance economic growth, including growth in less financially developed countries, whereas Chami (2003) found that remittances have a negative effect on economic growth. Chami's (2003) study is of particular importance for this paper because it argues that remittances' negative effect on economic growth stems from moral hazard problems. With an inflow of money from others, the recipients can decrease the effort they exert in labour, creating a disincentive to work. Targeting the elderly, who no longer work, can minimise the risk of moral hazard.

5. The Model

This section develops a theoretical model to support the new aid modality that we propose in this paper. The offset of the model is that subsidising consumption can spur output in a poor country. The subsidy (cash transfer) is conditioned on age and only elderly individuals are entitled. The purpose of the conditional transfer for the elderly is to stimulate

the labour supply and thereby output in the economy. For this mechanism to be effective there must be an underutilised workforce such that the economy initially does not use its production possibilities.

To illustrate the way in which a conditional nominal transfer affects economic growth, we applied an overlapping generations model without physical capital. Excluding capital markets impedes persistent growth but maintains temporary growth effects and long-run level effects. The rationale for this simplification stems from the structure of the markets that we are considering.

Traditionally, low saving rates, a lack of sufficient education and political systems, poorly managed institutions, a poor macroeconomic environment and slow technological progress are considered as important explanations for low income and scarce economic development. Nevertheless, in several underdeveloped countries, the utilisation of the labour force is also suboptimal. This factor limits the production possibilities and keeps economic growth below its potential. There are two main reasons as to why workers may be drawn away from market activities. First, wages in the labour market are relatively low, possibly because of low demand and low market price for the final goods. Second, people are frequently needed in home activities, such as taking care of the elderly and supporting the family, and in farming activities that are not related to a market. Accordingly, workers consider an important trade-off between market activities and home activities, and the market wage provides important leverage in this decision.

5.1. Assumptions and preliminaries

This paper examines an infinite-horizon overlapping generations model, in which individuals have finite lifetimes. The overlapping generations model assumes that two generations are present in each period and is thus based on the seminal contributions of Allais (1947) and

Diamond (1965). In addition, the model is augmented in several respects to account for the different characteristics of low-income countries. Poor countries have similarities or characteristics that are useful in establishing the assumptions for the model.

The following characteristics are relevant. First, poor countries usually have a large amount of people and workers relative to capital, meaning that these countries usually have a comparative advantage in labour intensive production compared to more developed countries. Second, labour is underutilised because of both unemployment and underemployment. In relation to the transfer proposal, this paper is primarily concerned with underemployment. Addressing underemployment requires workers to have an alternative to market activities and to base their labour supply decisions on alternative cost considerations. Third, elderly people mainly consume goods such as food, health-care services, and if they have the opportunity, schooling services for their grandchildren. These goods are all characterised as highly labour-intensive and, to some degree, non-tradable. The production of these services in poor countries is therefore mainly based on labour. First-order effects on production because of stimulated demand will accordingly trigger production activities driven by labour. The demand for final goods is limited by poorly managed financial markets, which reduces the possibilities of borrowing money.

These characteristics motivate certain assumptions for the model. Because poor countries have a relatively large amount of labour and the purchasing pattern by the elderly is labour intensive, it is assumed that labour (L) is the only variable input factor in the production function. Accordingly, the production technology is shown by the following equation:

$$(1) \quad Y_t = F(L_t) = AL_t^\alpha,$$

where $A > 0$ and $\alpha \in (0,1]$ denote a technical scale parameter and the labour share, respectively. The restricted value on the labour share implies that the production function has positive and decreasing marginal productivity.

Because labour is underutilised, it is assumed that the economy is below the production possibilities frontier. This feature is expressed by the relation between working time and the total time available. We denote total time available as \bar{l}_t and the time devoted to labour market activities as the portion $\hat{l}_t \in (0, \bar{l}_t)$. Accordingly, individual leisure time is $l_t = \bar{l}_t - \hat{l}_t$. This scenario implies the following expression for capacity utilisation, $CU = \hat{l}_t / \bar{l}_t < 1$. The low utilisation of labour capacity is an incentive problem based on the low wages paid for work activities.

Low wage levels reflect situations in which the prices of goods and services are low enough to allow workers to allocate their time to home activities instead. Home activities create an alternative to market activities, and when people regard production for personal or household consumption as having a higher return than production for the market, working individuals prefer the former. These considerations presume that labour is idle and not fully utilised in market activities, so that motivating the labour force to increase its labour supply for the market is likely to stimulate economic growth. This mechanism requires that the labour supply is elastic and therefore endogenous.

The demographics in the model are described as follows. During each period t , N_t children are born, so at each period $t \geq 1$, $N_t + N_{t-1}$ individuals are alive. The population grows at a constant rate of $n > -1$, so that $N_{t+1} = (1 + n)N_t$.

5.2. Individual Behaviour and Endogenous Labour Supply

Consider an overlapping generations economy in which each generation consists of a continuum of identical individuals assumed to maximise lifetime utility. Each individual lives for two periods. In their first period, they elastically supply a portion, \hat{l}_t , of labour. In the second period of their lives, individuals are non-working and consume using their own savings. For simplicity, we restrict our model by assuming that an individual born in period t endogenously supplies labour during period t and consumes only in period $t + 1$ (Reichlin 1986; Duranton 2001). For analytical purposes, we assume a constant intertemporal elasticity of substitution (CIES) description of people's preference structure. The disutility of work and elderly-only consumption imply the following utility function:

$$(2) \quad u_t = u(l_t, c_{t+1}) = \left(l_t^{\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma}} + c_{t+1}^{\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma}} \right)^{\frac{\sigma}{\sigma-1}},$$

where c denotes consumption and $\sigma \neq 1$ is the elasticity of substitution. The conditional transfer to elderly people is modelled as a quantity subsidy on consumption. This approach is appropriate as long as the increase in purchasing power leads to higher demand and nothing is saved. The intertemporal budget constraint is therefore given by the following:

$$(3) \quad (P_{t+1} - s)c_{t+1} = w_t(\bar{l}_t - l_t),$$

where P_{t+1} is the price of goods bought in period $t + 1$, w_t is the wage rate, $s > 0$ is the subsidy, and the right-hand side therefore shows individual savings when young. It is assumed that the transfer to elderly people's consumption is less than the price of the good. It is unreasonable to subsidise a good more than it costs, hence $s < P_{t+1}$. In period t , the agent only has expectations about prices. However, in equilibrium, it is assumed that the consumers have perfect foresight. The maximisation of the utility function in (2) subject to the constraint

in (3), with respect to l_t and c_{t+1} , yields a dynamic optimisation problem. Setting the Lagrangean for this problem, we obtain

$$(4) \quad \Gamma(l_t, c_{t+1}, \lambda) = \left(l_t^{\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma}} + c_{t+1}^{\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma}} \right)^{\frac{\sigma}{\sigma-1}} - \lambda [(P_{t+1} - s)c_{t+1} + w_t l_t - w_t \bar{l}_t].$$

The first-order conditions of this problem imply that optimal demand for leisure and consumption is shown by the following:

$$(5) \quad l_t = \frac{\bar{l}_t}{1 + w_t^{\sigma-1} (P_{t+1} - s)^{1-\sigma}},$$

$$(6) \quad c_{t+1} = \frac{w_t \bar{l}_t}{P_{t+1} - s + w_t^{1-\sigma} (P_{t+1} - s)^{\sigma}}.$$

A partial equilibrium analysis of these first-order conditions provides important insight into the argument of the paper. First, it can be verified that an increase in the subsidy will increase the consumption by the elderly:

$$(7) \quad \frac{\partial c_{t+1}}{\partial s} = \frac{w_t \bar{l}_t [1 + \sigma w_t^{1-\sigma} (P_{t+1} - s)^{\sigma-1}]}{[P_{t+1} - s + w_t^{1-\sigma} (P_{t+1} - s)^{\sigma}]^2} > 0$$

as $s < P_{t+1}$. An increase in consumption by the elderly will stimulate producers to increase their supply of final goods. Such a change in supply is possible because the economy is beneath the production possibility frontier. Moreover, this feature also implies that supply is an increasing function of price; hence, the supply curve is increasing. Therefore, an increase in demand from the elderly will increase the price of the final good. To meet higher demand,

the producers require more labour, and an increase in the demand for labour will increase wages.

The next step in the argument is then to study the way in which a change in wages will affect the supply of labour. The relation between the wage rate and leisure demonstrates the partial change in labour supply as the wage rate responds to higher demand for labour. Differentiating the first-order condition in (5) with respect to the wage rate becomes

$$(8) \quad \frac{\partial l_t}{\partial w_t} = - \frac{(\sigma-1)\bar{l}_t w_t^{\sigma-2} (P_{t+1}-s)^{1-\sigma}}{[1+w_t^{\sigma-1} (P_{t+1}-s)^{1-\sigma}]^2} \begin{cases} > 0 & \text{if } \sigma < 1 \\ < 0 & \text{if } \sigma > 1 \end{cases}$$

Hence, the sign of this derivative depends on the size of the elasticity of substitution. Because we are considering growth-promoting strategies in poor, low-income countries, it is reasonable to assume that leisure and consumption are gross substitutes, i.e., $\sigma > 1$ (Duranton 2001, de-Mel, McKenzie et al. forthcoming). We make this assumption for the rest of the paper. From equation (8), $\sigma > 1$ implies that an increase in the wage rate in the market reduces the demand for leisure and thereby increases the labour supply. Accordingly, the introduction of a subsidy stimulates the demand for services and thereby prices and wages. Workers will be motivated to increase their supply in the market, and capacity utilisation will increase.

5.3. Firms

The production technology in the economy is given by the production function in (1). Recall that the production function has positive and decreasing marginal productivity. This feature impedes perpetual economic growth. However, long-run level effects and transitional growth effects on production are possible. Given the wage rate and the product price, producers choose the level of labour with which to maximise profits, $\pi_t = P_t A L_t^\alpha - w_t L_t$. The economy

is assumed to be perfectly competitive, and the first-order condition of a representative producer is shown by

$$(9) \quad \alpha P_t A L_t^{\alpha-1} = w_t,$$

where the left-hand side is the marginal revenue. The factor demand function is therefore

$$(10) \quad L_t = \left[\frac{\alpha A P_t}{w_t} \right]^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha}}.$$

From equation (10), it is straightforward to show that an increase in the product price increases the demand for labour.

5.4. Equilibrium and analysis

The present model economy has two markets, the final-goods market and the labour market.

The labour market equilibrium condition is derived by equalising the producer's labour demand (10) and the total labour supply:

$$(11) \quad L_t = \hat{l}_t N_t.$$

If $\hat{l}_t = \bar{l}_t$, then $l_t = 0$, and the agents devote all their time to working activities in the market. Leisure and the possibility for home production are then zero. However, as the capacity utilisation is assumed not to be full, $CU < 1$, and labour is therefore idle for market activities, i.e., $0 < l_t < \bar{l}_t$.

According to Walras' law, equilibrium in the labour market implies that of the final-product, or service, market:

$$(12) \quad Y_t = A(\hat{l}_t N_t)^\alpha = c_t N_{t-1},$$

where the right-hand side denotes consumption by elderly people in period t .

As mentioned earlier, age-conditional transfers to a selected segment of the population are likely to trigger demand for final goods and to increase prices and wages. To evaluate the way in which this policy interaction affects the economy's growth level, we must consider the effect of the subsidy on the production level in general equilibrium. By inserting the optimal demand for leisure (5) and the first-order condition in (9) into the production function in (12), the supply function becomes

$$(13) \quad Y_t = AN_t^\alpha \left[\bar{l}_t - \frac{\bar{l}_t}{1 + (\alpha AP_t L_t^{\alpha-1})(P_{t+1} - s)^{1-\sigma}} \right]^\alpha.$$

Differentiating equation (13) in respect to the subsidy yields the following:

$$(14) \quad \frac{\partial Y_t}{\partial s} = \underbrace{-\alpha AN_t^\alpha}_{(1)} \bar{l}_t \underbrace{(\alpha AP_t L_t^{\alpha-1})^{\sigma-1} (1-\sigma)(P_{t+1} - s)^{-\sigma}}_{(2)} \underbrace{\left[1 + (\alpha AP_t L_t^{\alpha-1})^{\sigma-1} (P_{t+1} - s)^{1-\sigma} \right]^{-2}}_{(3)} \times \left[\bar{l}_t - \frac{\bar{l}_t}{1 + (\alpha AP_t L_t^{\alpha-1})^{\sigma-1} (P_{t+1} - s)^{1-\sigma}} \right]^{\alpha-1} > 0.$$

The inequality follows because (1) < 0, (2) < 0, and (3) > 0. (1) < 0 follows immediately. (2)

< 0 follows because the numerator is negative as a result of $P_{t+1} > s$ and $\sigma > 1$. (3) > 0

follows because the denominator in the second term is greater than unity as a result of

$$P_{t+1} > s.$$

The result in equation (14) can be explained by the following arguments. An underlying argument in this paper is that one way to stimulate economic growth is to make use of the potential workforce. This approach will trigger production and increase output in the long run. Moreover, it is argued that increasing the wage will make it more attractive to work and hence increase labour supply. A nominal transfer to elderly individuals will boost their demand for consumption goods, which will increase the price of the good and thereby create an incentive to increase the supply. Furthermore, this scenario will increase the need for labour and therefore increase wages. Working activities in the market will then become more attractive, and the labour supply will increase.

Underemployed workers in the market comprise underutilised capacity and therefore lower the optimal production. Idle workers are usually considered to be inefficiencies in the economy. However, this may not be the case here because the workers may find it individually optimal to allocate their time to home-production activities rather than to activities in the market. The current model, however, assumes this behaviour to be influenced by changes in demand and wages. As the subsidy to elderly people increases demand and therefore leads to higher wages, workers will become stimulated to devote more time to the market and the labour supply therefore will increase based on the assumption of gross substitution. The effect on the labour supply is already shown to be in partial equilibrium, however. The same relationship holds in general equilibrium. Because the production is linked to labour only, the production level is likely to increase.

The first-order effects illustrated in this paper do not imply an increase in persistent growth, but they instead imply only short-term growth effects or growth in a transitional phase. This result is based on the simplicity of the production structure and on labour

assumed to have diminishing marginal productivity. This assumption is reasonable because capital eventually will be necessary in most production activities. However, second-order or multiplier effects should be observable because the increase in production should increase the workers' income and consequently stimulate their demand for final goods and, most likely, for input factors. The working individuals' demand for input factors and their consumption pattern are most likely different from those of elderly people and, consequently, will stimulate production in other sectors in the economy. In such a setting, it will be necessary to include capital markets.

6. Conclusions and Proposals for Further Research

This paper aims to stimulate debate by introducing an alternative mechanism for foreign development aid. With the help of an economic model, we demonstrate how direct cash transfers to elderly people can spur economic growth. Targeting all elderly people above a certain age minimises selection costs and removes perverse incentives (of remaining poor to continue receiving the benefit). The fact that most elderly people are retired and not in the labour market helps overcome moral-hazard problems. The original motivation for this paper stemmed from the rapid spread of mobile phones across Africa, a phenomenon that makes direct cash transfers across borders at a low cost feasible. Compared to the traditional foreign-aid regime, through which a minimal amount of aid reaches the end-beneficiaries, our proposed model ensures that nearly 100% of the money actually reaches the target beneficiaries, most of whom are among the poorest and live in the least developed countries. Moreover, our model illustrates that such transfers will trigger economic growth.

From an empirical point of view, the next step is to design and implement some geographically limited pilot schemes to test the idea. This can be done by transparent aid organisations with or without government coordination. One challenge will be the use of

public registries to verify recipients' ages, although this problem is gradually becoming manageable because national registers of residents in many countries have improved considerably in the past decade. Another challenge is related to annual renewals, which are needed to verify that the beneficiary is actually still alive. It will also be a challenge to determine at what age the transfer should start and thereby avoid becoming a disincentive to work. Local adaptations will be needed to address these challenges. In this paper, we suggest that by targeting elderly people, disincentives to work will be minimised. Nevertheless, we suggest observing whether the proposed cash transfers will reduce other family members' work efforts.

Regarding the applied model itself, one reasonable extension is to include the capital market. This inclusion would advance the production function and yield an opportunity to study long-run growth effects via capital accumulation. Moreover, interest rates would be a part of the model and would affect individual budget constraints. The consumption of both final goods and leisure would therefore depend on the interest rate. One complicated feature regarding overlapping-generation models with productive capital, augmented to include endogenous labour supply, is related to stability and indeterminacy. The existence of multiple equilibrium paths may, however, be addressed by imposing appropriate restrictions (Biggs, Snodgrass et al. 1991, Berenbach and Guzman 1994).

Another extension of the model would be to include consumption in each individual's first period of life. Such an extension would change both the utility function and the budget constraint. Rather than saving all of the income earned in the first period of life, individuals would then make adjustments to derive an optimal saving rate. This approach would affect both consumption and economic growth.

References

- Aborderin, I. (2004). "Decline in Material Family Support for Older People in Urban Ghana, Africa: Understanding Processes and Causes of Change." *The journals of Gerontology, Series B* 59(3): S128-S137.
- Barrientos, A., et al. (2003). "Old age poverty in developing countries: Contribution and dependence in later life." *World Development* 31(3): 555-570.
- Berenbach, S. and D. Guzman (1994). The solidarity group experience worldwide. *The new world of microenterprise finance*. M. Otero and E. Rhyne. West Hartford, CT, Kumarian: 119-139.
- Biggs, T. S., et al. (1991). "On minimalist credit programs." *Savings and Development* 15(1): 39-52.
- Caldes, N. and J. A. Maluccio (2004). The cost of conditional cash transfers. *Economic and sector study series*. Washington, Inter American Development Bank: 1-25.
- Chami, R. (2003). Are immigrant remittance flows a source of capital for development? *IMF Working Paper*. Washington, IMF: 1-47.
- Clifton, J. (2012). "Editorial." *Journal of Economic Policy Reform* 15(1): 1-4.
- de-Mel, S., et al. (forthcoming). "Returns to capital in microenterprises: evidence from a field experiment." *Quarterly Journal of Economics*.
- Dunford, C. (2002). Building Better Lives: Sustainable Integration of Microfinance and Education in Child Survival, Reproductive Health and HIV/AIDS Prevention for the Poorest Entrepreneurs. *Pathways out of poverty*. S. Daley-Harris. Connecticut, USA, Kumarian Press: 1-3.
- Duranton, G. (2001). "Endogenous labour supply, growth and overlapping generations." *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization* 44: 295-314.
- Farrington, J. and R. Slater (2006). "Introduction: Cash transfers: Panacea for poverty reduction or money down the drain?" *Development Policy Review* 24(5): 499-211.
- Grosh, M. (1994). Administering targeted social programs in Latin America: From platitude to practice. *Regional and Sectoral Studies*. Washington, World Bank: 1-188.
- Halder, S. R. (2003). "Poverty outreach and BRAC's microfinance interventions: Programme impact and sustainability." *IDS Bulletin* 34(4): 44-53.
- Hanlon, J., et al. (2010). *Just give money to the poor: The development revolution from the Global South*. Sterling, VA, USA, Kumarian Press.
- ITU (2011). The World in 2011. ICT Facts and figures. Geneva, Switzerland, ITU World Telecommunication.

- Khandker, S. (2005). "Micro-Finance and Poverty: Evidence Using Panel Data from Bangladesh." *World Bank Economic Review* 19(2): 263-286.
- Lagarde, M., et al. (2007). "Conditional cash transfer for improving uptake of health interventions in low- and middle-income countries - A systematic review." *Journal of the American Medical Association* 298(16): 1900-1910.
- Lin, J. Y. and D. Rosenblatt (2012). "Shifting patterns of economic growth and rethinking development." *Journal of Economic Policy Reform* 15(3): 171-194.
- Maes, J. and L. Foose (2006). Microfinance and non-financial services for the very poor. Washington, Seep Network - Poverty outreach working group.
- McGillivray, M., et al. (2006). "Controversies over the impact of development aid: It works; it doesn't; it can, but that depends..." *Journal of International Development* 18: 1031-1050.
- OECD (2008). "OECD journal on development: Development cooperation report 2007." *Development cooperation report* 9(1): 1-238.
- Pickens, M., Porteous D. and Rotman S., (2009). Banking the poor via G2P payments. *Focus Notes*. Washington, CGAP. 58.
- Rao, M. (2011). Mobile Africa Report 2011, Mobile Monday - www.mobilemonday.net.
- Schubert, B. and J. Goldberg (2004). The pilot social cash transfer scheme: Kalomo district, Zambia. Lusaka, GTZ.
- Schubert, B. and R. Slater (2006). "Social cash transfers in low-income African countries: Conditional or unconditional?" *Development Policy Review* 24(5): 571-578.
- Setterfield, M. (2002). *The economics of demand-led growth*. UK, Edward Elgar.
- Shetty, P. (2012). "Grey matter: Ageing in developing countries." *The Lancet* 379(9823): 1285-1287.
- UN (2006). *Building Inclusive Financial Sectors for Development*. New York, United Nations.
- UNFPA (2012). Aging in the twenty-first century: A celebration and a challenge. New York and London, United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) and HelpAge International.
- World-Bank (1997). Burkina Faso: Le project de promotion du petit credit rural, sustainable banking for the poor. Washington, World Bank.